

A STABLE AGRICULTURAL SYSTEM AS A CRITICAL PART OF THE ECONOMY

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Abstract: This article provides for agriculture as one of the main arteries of the economy. And stabilizing the agricultural system will help develop not only the standard of living of residents, but will also help multiply income several times.

Key words: agriculture, economics, stabilization.

Nowadays, agriculture is given due attention all over the world, because this industry is fundamental in the agro-industrial complex. Agriculture is a vital part of the economy. It produces products vital to society and has enormous economic potential. The level of agricultural development largely determines the state of the entire national economic potential, the socio-economic situation in society and the level of food security. The peculiarities of the agricultural system and other factors have led to the fact that the agriculture of many countries cannot satisfy their food needs. To this day, the proportion of the population that does not receive adequate nutrition remains very large. The development of agricultural sectors today requires investment activity and provision of the necessary financial and material resources to enterprises. Investments are long-term investments for the acquisition of fixed assets and working capital in the process of economic activity with the aim of making a profit. Investments are funds, securities, property rights that have a monetary value, invested in business objects for the purpose of profit or achieving another useful effect.

The issue of investment in agricultural business in the world at the moment is very difficult. On the one hand, while the world's leading countries invest billions of dollars in programs for the development of their agriculture, our country, with its enormous potential for agricultural land, occupies a far from leading position in agricultural production. Among large investors it is not at all easy to find people who would like to engage in agriculture, although the presence of more than a quarter of a million farms suggests that in our country there are still those who are ready to live, work and earn money in agricultural production. On the other hand, recently there has been more and more talk that

the growing demand for food is making the agricultural business more and more profitable, and the situation with investments in the agricultural sector is increasingly positive.

The UN does not include agriculture either in the list of leaders in investment efficiency or in the list of outsiders, and this is perhaps the most reasonable description of the Russian agricultural market. In fact, stagnation and stagnation have been observed in the global agricultural business in recent years. Therefore, the state's agricultural policy should largely be aimed at stimulating investment in agriculture. As practice shows, investments in agriculture are growing with budgetary support from the state. It is also necessary to change the pessimistic attitude of investors towards agriculture, since due to rising world food prices, the importance of agriculture in general is increasing. Among the main factors influencing the prospects for agricultural development are the following:

1. The right to acquire land ownership. Currently, land can be bought and sold.
2. Creating conditions for attracting borrowed funds. Money is allocated from the federal and local budgets to subsidize interest costs on servicing loans associated with investments in agriculture.
3. Tax benefits. Agriculture is the only sector where tax incentives apply and there are no additional fees (for example: excise tax, mineral extraction tax).
4. Import regulation.
5. Export barriers. The government uses various methods to restrict the export of agricultural products in order to control supplies and prices in the domestic market.
6. Interventions in the grain market. In order to influence prices on the country's domestic market, the Ministry of Agriculture created a special fund. Its grain reserves are replenished through government purchases during harvest years.
7. Investments in agricultural production. Investing money allows Russian companies to receive subsidies and also guarantees them preferential tax treatment. Moreover, investments in grain production reduce raw material costs and production costs, of course, if the value chain involves further processing, or if it is used as a raw material.
8. Investment in land. It is clear that prices do not reflect its real value, so you can purchase farmland as an asset that is growing in value and is capable of generating growing cash flows. In addition, land can be used as collateral to obtain cheaper loans.

9. Infrastructure development. High world grain prices provide an opportunity for Russian producers to enter export markets. However, you can face risks in farming.

For example, seasonality, lack of money at the initial stage of the investment cycle, shortage of fertilizers, fuels and lubricants, etc. Risk insurance in agriculture can be a way out of this situation. Thus, agriculture in Russia requires constant support from the state. It is necessary to develop development programs that will have a beneficial effect on agriculture. This industry is becoming profitable and thereby attracting investors.

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